

Analysis of distributed optical fiber sensor performance and its applications

Author¹ Shivprakash Palhewar, Research Scholar, RGPV Bhopal

Author² Dr. Anubhuti Khare, Guide & Professor, ECE Department, RGPV Bhopal

Abstract: - In this review paper we present review of the distributed optical fiber sensor. Distributed optical fiber sensors are devices that use optical fiber as sensing elements to measure physical parameters such as pressure, temperature, strain, acoustics, and other measurements. These devices provide continuous, distributed, and real-time monitoring. Distributed optical fiber sensors (DOFS) and fiber Bragg grating (FBG) have been used in various applications in various industries due to their unique ability to provide continuous, distributed, and real-time monitoring across various industries, contributing to improved safety, efficiency, and reliability of systems and structures. These sensors are preferred for designing optical sensor for structure health monitoring, optical sensor in the oil industry, and the gas industry as chemical sensor. Based on the published research article, we have conclusion according to scattering such as, Brillouin-scattering, Raman scattering, and Rayleigh scattering.

Keywords: - Optical sensor, grating, FBG, DOFS, Rayleigh scattering, Brillouin scattering, Raman scattering.

- 1 **Introduction:** - In the 23rd century of the modern life we all are surrounded by different types of sensors. Maximum sensors used by us in daily life mostly based on the principle of electromagnetic affect such type sensors are known as electromagnetic sensors property of such sensor may get affected by electromagnetic interference. Optical sensors have the unique advantage that free from electromagnetic interference, along with various inherent advantages such as small sensor size, low cost, high sensitivity, high accuracy, and real-time monitoring of speed and strain [1]. Nowadays FBGs are used in various applications in the field of laser technology, optical fiber communication, and optical sensor systems for example in-fiber mirror or narrow band optical fiber filters, strain and temperature sensors. To make optical fiber as an optical fiber sensor this is done by creating the grating inside the core of optical fiber. Inscribing bragg grating in optical fiber is formidable task, Optical

fiber Bragg grating is a combination of periodic and non-periodic modulation of the refractive index [2].

- 1.1 **Principle and overview of fiber Bragg gating:** - Optical fiber bragg grating reflect wave at a specific wavelength that is based on Bragg condition which is given by

$$\lambda_B = 2n_{eff} \Lambda \tag{Equation 1}$$

Where, λ_B = Bragg wavelength, n_{eff} = Effective refractive index, Λ = Spatial period of grating structure.

- 1.2 **Types of fiber Bragg grating:-** Various type of grating structure are used now a days in the field of fiber sensing, different fiber grating are having different property as well application or combination.

- 1.2.1 **Uniform fiber grating:-** this type of fiber grating structure the modulation of refractive index is content along its length of fiber. A typical structure of uniform grating with typical input wave spectrum transmitted wave spectrum and reflected wave spectrum are shown in Figure 1. To design different types of SM optical fibers and fibers coating are used with grating length is approximately 0.5 mm to 10 mm for application of temperature rang (-40 °C to +100 °C) the Acrylate coating is used, for high temperature rang (300°C and 500°C polyimide or metal (Cu, Al) coating are used respectively [3][4].

Figure 1 Uniform fiber grating structure with typical input, transmitted and reflected spectrum [5].

1.2.2 **Chirped fiber grating:** - Chirped fiber brgg grating have varying periodicity along the grating’s length. These FBGs are fabricated using a UV beam and a phase mask to create the desired index modulation. [6]. Chirped fiber grating offer better scattering compensator to improve Q-factor and minimization of bit error rate (BER) [7].

Figure 2 Chirped fiber grating structure with incident and reflected wave [6].

1.2.3 **Log-periodic fiber grating:-** In this fiber grating structure the modulation of refractive index along the length of fiber and the period of modulation use the logarithmic scale. Log-periodic fiber grating (LPFG) can be fabricated using various technique, such as UV exposure, phase mask method or point to point inscription [8]. Applications band – rejection filters, gain- flattening filters [9]

Figure 3 Log-periodic structure typical transmitted wave.

- 1.2.4 **Tilted fiber grating (TFG):-** In this type of fiber grating a specialized type of optical fiber grating structure is used where the grating lines or periodic structure are intentionally tilted or inclined with respect to fiber axis [10].

Figure 4 Tilted fiber grating structure

- 1.3 **Fabrication technique of grating:-** There are few popular grating writing technique such as (i) interferometer fabrication technique (ii) Phase mask technique (iii) Point-by-point fabrication of Bragg gratings (iv) Mask image projection [11] [12].
- 2 **Introduction of Distributed optical fiber sensor (DOFS):** - Distributed optical fiber sensor is a combination of multiple point sensors along the length of optical fiber. The complete length of optical fiber is treated as a sensor and they are capable of sensing multiple physical parameters. DOFS provide (a) Location (where), (b) different properties (average strain and/or temperature), (c) Magnitude (how much), and (d) Real time. Distributed sensing technologies having, the biggest market shears in today global market of sensor and in the upcoming years over the global market. The distributed optical sensor world market is calculated as 1.44 billion (USD) for the year 2022 and it is predicted to increase by 6.8% annual growth rate for the year 2020 to year 2023[13]. Distributed optical sensors have the following features that make them popular in the field of optical sensors [14].
- 2.1 **Principle and overview of Distributed optical fiber sensor:** - DOFS operate based on the principle of using the entire length of an optical fiber as sensing element. These sensors enable continuous and spatially distributed measurements along the length of fiber. There are several principles and techniques used in distributed optical fiber sensors, and two

common approaches are distributed temperature sensing (DTS) and distributed strain sensing (DSS). In optical fiber the scattering of light is a random statistical phenomenon which is applicable in all angular directions. Different types of scattering of light such as Rayleigh, Brillouin, and Raman scattering as shown in Figure 5. The central peak at the incident light frequency is called Rayleigh scattered light[15]

Figure 5 A typically light scattering spectrums[15].

2.2 **Classification of distributed fiber optical sensor:** - Distributed optical fiber sensors (DOFS) can be classified based on optical scattering like Rayleigh-based optical sensors, Brillouin-based optical sensors, and Raman-based optical sensors[16]. Based on this technique distributed fiber sensors have various applications in different fields. Distributed optical fiber sensors are classified as shown in Figure 6

Figure 6 Classification of distributed optical fiber sensor

2.2.1 Introduction of Brillouin scattering:- Brillouin scattering is a non-linear characteristic of optical material. An incident light to the core of an optical fiber can be converted into a scattered photon due to variations in temperature and strain changes in the effective refractive index. Low power and low frequency (Brillouin frequency Shift) back-scattered wave is received at the source end. There are two types of Brillouin scattering, spontaneous Brillouin scattering and Stimulated Brillouin scattering [17][18]. Brillouin scattering is used in structure health monitoring (SHM)[18], to detect larger changes in temperature and strain Brillouin technique-based sensor is a better technique in the area of distributed optical fiber sensors to monitor gas pipeline[19]. Brillouin scattering optical fiber sensors have advanced into high-speed and high-resolution systems for identifying and characterizing dynamic strain events in civil structures and materials [7][20]. Machine learning approaches have been integrated into Brillouin distributed fiber optic sensors (DFOSs), resulting in enhanced temperature, strain, and humidity measurements without increasing the system's cost [21]. Raman amplification can extend the sensing distance of distributed Brillouin optical fiber sensors, and window functions can improve the tradeoff between sensing distance and signal-to-noise ratio (SNR)[22]. Fiber-optic sensors based on the Mandelstam - Brillouin scattering principle can function in the time or frequency domain, with systems of the first category having better metrological characteristics in terms of spatial resolution and measurement errors [23]. Forward Brillouin scattering interactions support the sensing and analysis of media outside the cladding boundaries of standard fibers, enabling point-sensing and analysis of refractive index perturbations.

2.2.2 BOTDR:- BOTDR play a role in various measurement such as monitoring of strain in a line using commercial BOTDR at room temperature [24]. Wavelength diversity is used to reduce the effect of non-linearity but wavelength diversity reduces the performance. Wavelength diversity also improves the signal-to-noise ratio, the performance of this technique-based sensor can be improved further using with pulse coding and Raman amplification [25].

2.2.3 **BOTDA:-** This is used when light frequency distribution is generated due to Brillouin scattering [26]. In this type of sensing system uniform SNR is needed to avoid uneven Brillouin gain, and to increase the performance wavelength diversity techniques are used. Brillouin scattering-based optical fiber sensors are widely used in various industries due to their long sensing range and number of parameter measurements along the optical fiber cable [27]. Using Brillouin-scattering we will be able to detect temperature and strain with optical fiber. Due to various advantages Brillouin-based distributed fiber sensors have gained more attention in the sensing of temperature in the last two decades [28].

2.3 **Introduction of Raman scattering:** - In this type, we will send the light through the optical fiber, Raman scattering is generated if there are temperature changes that will produce backscattered light back to the direction of incoming light or toward the source in Stokes-band. By comparing the intensity of backscattered light in the Stokes and anti-stokes bands, we will be able to calculate the temperature with less error including the location. The measurement of temperature in distributed sensing is based on the Spontaneous Raman Scattering (SRS) effect. A laser Pulse of high power with a narrow width is incident on the sensing optical fiber; the laser pulse interacts with the molecules of optical fiber and generates extremely weak backscattered light [29].

Figure 7 Raman scattering [29]

Raman scattering based optical fiber sensors are popular nowadays in the field of sensors for the measurement of temperature. For the measurement of temperature under 300°C using the RODTR standard optical fiber is used to get the measurement of higher temperature more than 300°C normally used optical fiber is not suitable for higher temperature measurement a metal-coated optical fiber are used to maintain their physical and optical properties gold-coated multimedia fiber are used[17][30]. Distributive temperature sensing (DTS) is widely deployed in various industries. Raman scattering optical frequency domain reflectometry are used in the fire detection in tunnel or railway tunnel[31], highways, underground electrical transmission line, in industrial plant [32]. In this technique due to two-way attenuation and low scattering cross sections in the fiber weak signal Anti Stokes and Stokes signal received. To get an accurate result from wavelet transform are used in various Raman-based optical frequency domain temperature sensors [33]. Raman scattering is observed in a tapered silicon core fiber, with both spontaneous and stimulated effects presented. A peak gain of 0.8 dB is achieved with a 58.5 mW telecom pump.[34]. Raman scattering optical fiber sensors have been the focus of research in recent studies. One approach is the use of co-directional Raman pumping Brillouin optical time-domain reflect meter (BOTDR) with window functions to improve the tradeoff between sensing distance and signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) [22]. Another study explores the use of fiber-optics with roughened surfaces as efficient alternatives for fiber-optics based surface-enhanced Raman scattering (FO-SERS) sensing platforms, which can significantly increase the SERS intensity and SNR values [35].

- 2.4 **Introduction of Rayleigh-scattering:** - Rayleigh scattering is a phenomenon where photons are scattered by sub-wavelength objects, such as small particles or molecules. It is considered to be an elastic scattering process, meaning that the energy of the photons is conserved during scattering. In this type of scattering of light is random within the core of optical fiber. Rayleigh scattering concept is demonstrated with different types of testing schemes e.g. Optical Time Domain Reflectometry (OTDR) this will result in getting the position or location of changes of physical parameters. The monitoring of vibrations along the single mode fibers phase sensitive optical time-domain reflectometry (Φ -OTDR) technique is effective and simple[36]. TE- Φ OTDR technology provides high-resolution sensing in the cm scale. - TE- Φ OTDR requires low detection and acquisition bandwidths

[37]. A distributed optical fiber sensor for a vibration sensing system based on Rayleigh backscattering, and principle coherent detection, was demostred. Multiple vibration over the length of optical fiber static type as well as moving type. Using a single-fiber system sensing range above 90 km and with a two-fiber unit sensing range of more than 150 km is achieved. This type of sensing is used to detect the movement of trains, cars, persons, ground gidding, drilling, and hammering [38]. Comprehensive theoretical model of Rayleigh scattering - Review of applications and limitations of Rayleigh-based DOFS [39]. To detect the displacement using distributed optical fiber sensing is done by calculating the difference between the reflected signal and signal of reference. The range of displacement using distributed fiber sensing is several millimeters [40]. The scattering observables can be expressed in terms of the electric and magnetic complex scattering amplitudes, which can be independently benchmarked through experiments [41]. Rayleigh scattering can be used as an analytical technique for the detection of scattered particles, such as proteins. A physical shading method based on the Rayleigh scattering pattern has been developed, which improves the sensitivity, linearity, detection limit, precision, and accuracy of the detection process[42]. Additionally, a quantum theory of atomic Rayleigh scattering has been developed, which shows that an entangled state of the excited atom and the incident photon is formed during scattering[43]. To eliminate or reduce the interference of Rayleigh scattering in spectral resolution, missing data recovery coupled with principal component analysis or parallel factor analysis can be used as a strategy for Rayleigh scattering correction[43].

All the above techiques are used for various physical parameter dectecion and monitoring. Anti-stokes and stokes are important signals in distributed fiber sensing. For example to detect temperature and strain anti-stokes and stokes relation in signal intensity v/s signal frequency.

- 3 **Application of distributed optical fiber sensor (DOFS):** - Distributed Optical Fiber Sensors (DOFS) have various applications across different industries due to their various property and unique ability to provide continuous and distributed measurements along the length of the optical fiber. Here are some notable applications of distributed optical fiber

sensors from the various published research article.

- 3.1 **Structural Health Monitoring (SHM):-** To monitor the health and integrity of large civil structures like bridges, dams, buildings and pipelines [44]. Distributed optical fiber sensor can detect strain, temperature, and deformation along the entire length of the structure, and providing real-time monitoring on structural conditions.
- 3.2 **Oil and Gas Sector:-** Various applications are found in the industry of oil and gas sector for monitoring pipelines, storage of oil and gas wells. They can detect temperature changes, strain, and potential leaks in pipelines, enhancing the safety and efficiency of oil and gas operations [45][46][47][48].
- 3.3 **Power Sector /Smart Grids:-** Distributed optical fiber sensor are employed in the power industry for monitoring and controlling smart grids. To take the measurement of temperature and strain in power cables, helping to identify potential issues and prevent failures. Now a days the effective use of DOFS is used for real time monitoring of transformer [49].
- 3.4 **Geotechnical Monitoring:-** DOFS are used in geotechnical applications to monitor the stability of slopes, tunnels, and other underground structures [50]. They can provide early warnings for potential landslides or ground movements.
- 3.5 **Environmental Monitoring:-** Distributed optical fiber sensors can be utilized for environmental monitoring in applications such as detecting and locating oil spills, monitoring temperature changes in oceans, and assessing the impact of climate change on ecosystems [51].
- 3.6 **Aerospace Industry:-** DOFS play a role in monitoring the structural health of aircraft and spacecraft. They can detect strain, temperature, and vibrations, providing critical information for maintenance and ensuring the safety of aerospace vehicles [52].

- 3.7 **Industrial Process Monitoring:-** In industrial settings, DOFS can monitor various parameters such as temperature, pressure, and strain in real-time. This is particularly useful in manufacturing processes where precise control and monitoring are essential.[49][53]
- 3.8 **Medical Applications:-** Distributed optical fiber sensors are used in medical applications for monitoring physiological parameters within the body. For example, they can be integrated into catheters for temperature or pressure sensing in medical procedures [51].
- 3.9 **Security and Perimeter Monitoring:-** DOFS can be deployed for security purposes to monitor perimeters of critical infrastructure, military installations, or sensitive areas. They can detect and locate disturbances or intrusion [54].
- 3.10 **Fire Detection:-** Distributed optical fiber sensors can be used for early detection of fires in environments where traditional methods may not be suitable. They can sense temperature changes and hotspots, providing a quick response to potential fire incidents [55].
- 4 **Conclusion:** - above applications of fiber Bragg grating and distributed optical fiber sensor are used in various industries, the versatility of distributed optical fiber sensors in providing continuous, distributed, and real-time monitoring across various industries, contributing to improved safety, efficiency, and reliability of systems and structures. Based on the published research article we have conclusion according to scattering such as, Brillouin-scattering, Raman-scattering, and Rayleigh-scattering.
- a) Suitable for long distances and able to detect multiple physical parameters at a time.
 - b) These sensors are preferred for designing optical sensor for structure health monitoring, optical sensor in the oil industry, and the gas industry as chemical sensor.

5 Reference Papers:-

- [1] M. L. Filograno *et al.*, "Real-time monitoring of railway traffic using fiber Bragg grating sensors," *IEEE Sens. J.*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 85–92, 2012, doi: 10.1109/JSEN.2011.2135848.

- [2] R. Chitaree and W. Talataisong, "The period sensitivity and modal sensitivity of optical fiber force sensor based on mechanical induced ultra-long period fiber grating," *ICOCON 2016 - 2016 15th Int. Conf. Opt. Commun. Networks*, pp. 15–17, 2017, doi: 10.1109/ICOCON.2016.7875783.
- [3] J. Li and M. Zhang, "Physics and applications of Raman distributed optical fiber sensing," *Light Sci. Appl.*, vol. 11, no. 1, 2022, doi: 10.1038/s41377-022-00811-x.
- [4] S. Drusová, W. Bakx, A. D. Wexler, and H. L. Offerhaus, "Possibilities for groundwater flow sensing with fiber bragg grating sensors," *Sensors (Switzerland)*, vol. 19, no. 7, pp. 1–15, 2019, doi: 10.3390/s19071730.
- [5] T. Saktioto and J. Ali, "Non Linear Optic in Fiber Bragg Grating," *Sel. Top. Opt. Fiber Technol.*, no. May, 2012, doi: 10.5772/35250.
- [6] M. Guy and Y. Painchaud, "Fiber Bragg gratings: A versatile approach to dispersion compensation," *Photonics Spectra*, vol. 38, no. 8, pp. 96–101, 2004.
- [7] N. Basil and M. Moutaz, "Design and Implementation of Chirp Fiber Bragg Grating for Long Haul Transmission System using Opti-system," *Inform. Appl. Mach. Electr. Electron. Comput. Sci. Commun. Syst.*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 1–07, 2021, doi: 10.47812/IJAMECS2020101.
- [8] D. Sengupta and G. Rajan, "Introduction to optical fiber sensors," in *Structural Health Monitoring of Composite Structures Using Fiber Optic Methods*, 2016, pp. 41–68. doi: 10.1201/9781315369815.
- [9] D. Sáez-Rodríguez, J. L. Cruz, A. Díez, and M. V Andrés, "Coupling between counterpropagating cladding modes in fiber Bragg gratings.," *Opt. Lett.*, vol. 36 8, pp. 1518–1520, 2011, [Online]. Available: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:207341252>
- [10] Y. Singh, S. K. Raghuvanshi, O. Prakash, and P. K. Saini, "Design and development of tilted fiber Bragg grating (TFBG) chemical sensor with regression analysis of grating parameters for sensitivity optimization," *Opt. Quantum Electron.*, vol. 53, no. 11, p. 664, 2021, doi: 10.1007/s11082-021-03328-6.
- [11] A. Othonos, "Faser-Bragg gratings," *Rev. Sci. Instrum.*, vol. 68, no. 12, pp. 4309–4341, 1997.
- [12] A. Srivastava, F. Esposito, S. Campopiano, and A. Iadicicco, "Fabrication and characterization of long period gratings in pure-silica fibers," vol. 11028, p. 94, 2019, doi: 10.1117/12.2521604.
- [13] D. Fiber, O. Sensor, M. Size, B. Application, and S. Forecasts, "COVID-19 Impact Insights," 2023.
- [14] C. Gables, "White Paper Distributed Temperature Sensing (DTS)," pp. 1–8.
- [15] P. Lu *et al.*, "Distributed optical fiber sensing: Review and perspective," *Appl. Phys. Rev.*, vol. 6, no. 4, 2019, doi: 10.1063/1.5113955.
- [16] J. K. Sahota, N. Gupta, and D. Dhawan, "Fiber Bragg grating sensors for monitoring of physical parameters: a comprehensive review," *Opt. Eng.*, vol. 59, no. 06, p. 1, 2020, doi: 10.1117/1.oe.59.6.060901.
- [17] I. Laarossi *et al.*, "Ultrahigh Temperature Raman-Based Distributed Optical Fiber Sensor with Gold-Coated Fiber," *IEEE J. Sel. Top. Quantum Electron.*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 296–301, 2017, doi: 10.1109/JSTQE.2016.2633821.
- [18] C. A. Galindez-Jamioy and J. M. López-Higuera, "Brillouin distributed fiber sensors: An overview and applications," *J. Sensors*, vol. 2012, 2012, doi: 10.1155/2012/204121.

- [19] I. Ashry *et al.*, “A Review of Distributed Fiber-Optic Sensing in the Oil and Gas Industry,” *J. Light. Technol.*, vol. 40, no. 5, pp. 1407–1431, 2022, doi: 10.1109/JLT.2021.3135653.
- [20] K. Song and J. H. Kim, “Super-speed high-resolution distributed Brillouin sensor for mapping strain waves propagating an optical ber,” 2023.
- [21] C. Karapanagiotis and K. Krebber, “Machine Learning Approaches in Brillouin Distributed Fiber Optic Sensors,” *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 13, p. 6187, Jul. 2023, doi: 10.3390/s23136187.
- [22] Q. Huang, Y. Bao, J. Sun, and C. Huang, “Distributed Brillouin optical fiber sensors assisted by first-order Raman amplification with window functions,” *Opt. Lasers Eng.*, vol. 164, p. 107504, May 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.optlaseng.2023.107504.
- [23] I. V. Bogachkov, N. I. Gorlov, and T. I. Monastyrskaya, “Types and Applications of Fiber-Optic Sensors Based on the Mandelstam - Brillouin Scattering Principle,” in *Proceedings of the 2022 International Conference on Information, Control, and Communication Technologies, ICCT 2022*, Oct. 2022, pp. 1–4. doi: 10.1109/ICCT56057.2022.9976757.
- [24] X. Ouyang, X. Zou, L. Chen, Z. Wei, and L. Yang, “Strain Monitoring of Overhead Transmission Line Based on Brillouin Scattering,” *J. Phys. Conf. Ser.*, vol. 2503, no. 1, 2023, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/2503/1/012032.
- [25] N. Lalam, W. P. Ng, X. Dai, Q. Wu, and Y. Q. Fu, “Performance analysis of Brillouin optical time domain reflectometry (BOTDR) employing wavelength diversity and passive depolarizer techniques,” *Meas. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 29, no. 2, 2018, doi: 10.1088/1361-6501/aa9c6e.
- [26] J. Liu, Y. Wang, Y. Lu, J. Wei, and D. P. Kanungo, “Application of distributed optical fiber sensing technique in monitoring the ground deformation,” *J. Sensors*, vol. 2017, 2017, doi: 10.1155/2017/6310197.
- [27] X. Zhang, Y. Lu, F. Wang, H. Liang, and Y. Zhang, “Development of fully-distributed fiber sensors based on brillouin scattering,” *Photonic Sensors*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 54–61, 2011, doi: 10.1007/s13320-010-0019-7.
- [28] W. P. Ng and N. Lalam, “Future of distributed fiber sensors (invited paper),” *ICOON 2016 - 2016 15th Int. Conf. Opt. Commun. Networks*, vol. 2017-March, pp. 1–3, 2017, doi: 10.1109/ICOON.2016.7932343.
- [29] M. Salah, A. Bereak, M. Gabry, T. Shaheen, and M. Kewan, “A holistic stimulation approach to unlock potential of horizontal open hole completion in tight carbonate: Optimization of acidizing treatment and successful diversion in real-time using distributed temperature sensing,” *Soc. Pet. Eng. - Abu Dhabi Int. Pet. Exhib. Conf. ADIPEC 2015*, no. November, 2015, doi: 10.2118/177800-ms.
- [30] M. Elsherif *et al.*, “Optical Fiber Sensors: Working Principle, Applications, and Limitations,” *Adv. Photonics Res.*, vol. 3, no. 11, 2022, doi: 10.1002/adpr.202100371.
- [31] G. Cedilnik, R. Hunt, and G. Lees, “Advances in train and rail monitoring with DAS,” *Opt. InfoBase Conf. Pap.*, vol. Part F124-, no. c, 2018, doi: 10.1364/ofs.2018.the35.
- [32] M. Kumar *et al.*, “Optics & Laser Technology Raman optical fiber distributed temperature sensor using wavelet transform based simplified signal processing of Raman backscattered signals,” *Opt. Laser Technol.*, vol. 65, pp. 14–24, 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.optlastec.2014.06.012.
- [33] M. K. Saxena *et al.*, “Empirical Mode Decomposition-Based Detection of Bend-Induced

- Error and Its Correction in a Raman Optical Fiber Distributed Temperature Sensor,” *IEEE Sens. J.*, vol. 16, no. 5, pp. 1243–1252, 2016, doi: 10.1109/JSEN.2015.2499242.
- [34] M. Huang *et al.*, “Stimulated Raman Scattering in a Tapered Submicron Silicon Core Fiber,” in *Conference on Lasers and Electro-Optics*, 2021, p. STh5A.3. doi: 10.1364/CLEO_SI.2021.STh5A.3.
- [35] M. Shin, kyunghun kim, and dae hong jeong, “Enhancement of the signal-to-noise ratio in fiber-optics based SERS detection by rough-cutting the end surface,” *Opt. Express*, vol. 31, no. 8, p. 12645, Apr. 2023, doi: 10.1364/oe.485021.
- [36] X. Bao and L. Chen, “Recent Progress in Distributed Fiber Optic Sensors,” *Sensors 2012, Vol. 12, Pages 8601-8639*, vol. 12, no. 7, pp. 8601–8639, Jun. 2012, doi: 10.3390/S120708601.
- [37] M. R. Fernandez-Ruiz, M. Soriano-Amat, V. Duran, H. F. Martins, S. Martin-Lopez, and M. Gonzalez-Herraez, “Time Expansion in Distributed Optical Fiber Sensing,” *J. Light. Technol.*, vol. 41, no. 11, pp. 3305–3315, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.1109/JLT.2023.3245218.
- [38] V. Novotný, P. Sysel, A. Prokeš, P. Hanák, K. Slavíček, and J. Přinosil, “Fiber optic based distributed mechanical vibration sensing,” *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 14, pp. 1–19, 2021, doi: 10.3390/s21144779.
- [39] L. Palmieri, L. Schenato, M. Santagiustina, and A. Galtarossa, “Rayleigh-Based Distributed Optical Fiber Sensing,” *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 18, p. 6811, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.3390/s22186811.
- [40] I. B. Kwon, C. Y. Kim, D. C. Seo, and H. C. Hwang, “Multiplexed fiber optic OTDR sensors for monitoring of soil sliding,” *18th IMEKO World Congr. 2006 Metrol. a Sustain. Dev.*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 151–154, 2006.
- [41] A. P. Vinogradov, V. Y. Shishkov, I. V. Doronin, E. S. Andrianov, A. A. Pukhov, and A. A. Lisiansky, “Quantum theory of Rayleigh scattering,” *Opt. Express*, vol. 29, no. 2, p. 2501, Jan. 2021, doi: 10.1364/OE.412852.
- [42] Z. Li, Y. Meng, H. Nie, R. Gu, X. Wang, and D. Xiao, “The unique physical shading pattern of Rayleigh scattering for the generally improved detection of scattering particles,” *Analyst*, vol. 147, no. 11, pp. 2361–2368, 2022, doi: 10.1039/D2AN00488G.
- [43] A. V. Volotka, A. Surzhykov, and S. Fritzsche, “Rayleigh scattering of linearly polarized light: Scenario of the complete experiment,” *Phys. Rev. A*, vol. 102, no. 4, p. 042814, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.1103/PhysRevA.102.042814.
- [44] A. Barrias, J. R. Casas, and S. Villalba, “A review of distributed optical fiber sensors for civil engineering applications,” *Sensors (Switzerland)*, vol. 16, no. 5, 2016, doi: 10.3390/s16050748.
- [45] H. S. Pradhan and P. K. Sahu, “A survey on the performances of distributed fiber-optic sensors,” *2015 Int. Conf. Microwave, Opt. Commun. Eng. ICMOCE 2015*, pp. 243–246, 2016, doi: 10.1109/ICMOCE.2015.7489736.
- [46] Z. Zhang *et al.*, “Recent progress in distributed optical fiber raman photon sensors at China Jiliang University,” *Photonic Sensors*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 127–147, 2012, doi: 10.1007/s13320-012-0056-5.
- [47] B. Arun Sundaram, S. Parivallal, and K. Kesavan, “Studies on Distributed Brillouin Scattering Technique for Monitoring of Lifeline Structures,” *J. Sci. Ind. Res. (India)*, vol. 80, no. 5, pp. 420–427, 2021, doi: 10.56042/jsir.v80i05.41784.
- [48] L. Pavesi, G. Bolognini, Y. Muanenda, C. J. Oton, and F. Di Pasquale, “Application of Raman and Brillouin Scattering Phenomena in Distributed Optical Fiber Sensing,” *Front.*

- Phys*, vol. 7, p. 155, 2019, doi: 10.3389/fphy.2019.00155.
- [49] P. Lu *et al.*, “Real-Time Monitoring of Temperature Rises of Energized Transformer Cores with Distributed Optical Fiber Sensors,” *IEEE Trans. Power Deliv.*, vol. 34, no. 4, pp. 1588–1598, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.1109/TPWRD.2019.2912866.
- [50] L. L. K. Cheung, K. Soga, P. J. Bennett, Y. Kobayashi, B. Amatya, and P. Wright, “Optical fibre strain measurement for tunnel lining monitoring,” *Proc. Inst. Civ. Eng. - Geotech. Eng.*, vol. 163, no. 3, pp. 119–130, Jun. 2010, doi: 10.1680/geng.2010.163.3.119.
- [51] A. Shadab, S. K. Raghuvanshi, and S. Kumar, “Advances in Micro-Fabricated Fiber Bragg Grating for Detection of Physical, Chemical, and Biological Parameters—A Review,” *IEEE Sens. J.*, vol. 22, no. 16, pp. 15650–15660, Aug. 2022, doi: 10.1109/JSEN.2022.3188813.
- [52] I. García, J. Zubia, G. Durana, G. Aldabaldetrekue, M. A. Illarramendi, and J. Villatoro, “Optical Fiber Sensors for Aircraft Structural Health Monitoring,” *Sensors*, vol. 15, no. 7, pp. 15494–15519, 2015, doi: 10.3390/s150715494.
- [53] H. J. Zhou, Y. Liao, and Z. Meng, “Distributed optical fiber sensing based on Brillouin scattering,” *Guangxue Jishu/Optical Tech.*, vol. 34, no. SUPPL., pp. 104–127, 2008, Accessed: Oct. 29, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://benthamopen.com/ABSTRACT/TOOPTSJ-7-104>
- [54] P. Dejdard, P. Závěška, S. Valach, P. Münster, and T. Horváth, “Image Edge Detection Methods in Perimeter Security Systems Using Distributed Fiber Optical Sensing,” *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 12, p. 4573, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.3390/s22124573.
- [55] J. Li *et al.*, “Long-Range Raman Distributed Fiber Temperature Sensor With Early Warning Model for Fire Detection and Prevention,” *IEEE Sens. J.*, vol. 19, no. 10, pp. 3711–3717, May 2019, doi: 10.1109/JSEN.2019.2895735.